

Numerical investigations on slender concrete-filled double-skin steel tubular columns using high-strength steels in fire

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ABSTRACT

Concrete-filled double-skin steel tubular (CFDST) elements have gained increasing attention in the last years thanks to its high bending stiffness and strength-to-weight ratio. This composite solution consists of an inner and outer steel tube and the sandwiched layer is filled with concrete. While the static behaviour is similar to the companion concrete-filled steel tubes (CFST), CFDST columns possess potentially higher fire resistances thanks to their sandwiched layer that shields the inner steel core. Unlike recent experimental and numerical studies, the current paper presents a CFDST column incorporating high-strength steels for the inner tube. This enables to limit the outer dimensions while keeping high values of slenderness. Additionally, the outer skin of this proposed solution is conceived to stabilize the inner elements without being directly loaded. Thus, the load is introduced directly onto the inner steel tube which is intended to transfer almost entirely the compression forces, especially in fire conditions. This latter aspect is of importance and it governs often the design of the member. To tackle this issue, a numerical model and the solver procedure is presented in this work. The preliminary simulations consist of heat transfer analyses followed by companion static analyses incorporating the temperature-dependent material properties. Upon validation of the model with existing test results, a parametric study is carried out to explore the performance of CFDST columns in fire. The geometry and materials of the proposed CFDST column integrating high-strength steels will be finally calibrated for the design of a foreseen fire test.

Keywords: Steel-concrete columns, Double-skin columns, Numerical modelling, Fire resistance

1 INTRODUCTION

New types of steel-concrete composite columns have been developed in recent years, including concrete-filled steel tubular (CFST) and concrete-filled steel double-skin tubular (CFDST) column. The latter is typically employed in design scenarios where high load-bearing capacity and stiffness are required, such as high-rise buildings, long-span bridges, towers and industrial buildings. These structural elements have gained popularity worldwide owing to their inherent advantages over traditional bare steel or reinforced concrete columns. The combination of both materials allows to exploit the following advantages: improved load-bearing capacity, fire resistance safety, cost effectiveness and ease of construction due to the absence of welded components inside the tubes.

The current research work focuses on the study of CFDST columns consisting of two concentric steel tubes where the sandwiched layer is filled with concrete (Fig. 1).

The behaviour of CFST columns has been extensively studied by several authors at ambient temperature [1, 2, 3] and in the event of fire [4, 5, 6], considering different geometries such as circular and square sections, high and low strength concrete, stub or slender columns. Tao et al. [7] and Li et al. [8] have conducted studies on CFDST columns where analytical formulae to determine the axial compressive capacity of different types of columns were proposed. Regarding the fire behaviour of CFDST columns, Han et al. [9], Wan et al. [10], and Mohd Zuki [11] presented experimental studies

and analytical solutions to derive the time-dependent temperature field and to calculate the resulting strength. Recently, Hui Lu et al. [12] conducted an in-depth numerical study and developed an accurate finite element (FE) model able to capture the fire behaviour of CFDST columns using conventional structural steels. However, research in the field of CFDST columns has several shortcomings due to the limited number of contributions available.

- 1 Outer steel tube
 - 2 Concrete interlayer
 - 3 Inner (high-strength) steel tube
- D_o Diameter of outer tube
 D_i Diameter of inner tube
 t_o Wall thickness of outer tube
 t_i Wall thickness of inner tube

Fig. 1: Cross-section of the concrete-filled double-skin steel tubular (CFDST) columns

2 MOTIVATION

As stated earlier, this article aims to investigate the behaviour of a new type of concrete-filled steel double skin tubular (CFDST) columns when subjected to fire conditions. The inner tube is intended to be made of high-strength steel whereas normal carbon steel is adopted for the outer tube. High-strength steels can indeed increase their resistance while enabling the use of slenderer columns with reduced cross-sections. Additionally, the sandwiched layer between the tubes represents another key parameter as it delays the heat transfer to the inner core. The latter is indeed the main load-bearing element in fire as a result of the early loss of stiffness and strength of the outer layer due to the elevated temperatures.

In consideration of the lack of evidence on the influence of materials of CFDST columns in fire, an appropriate three-dimensional finite element (FE) model accounting for the geometrical and material non-linearities is presented and the solving approach is thoroughly described in Section 4. The influence of key variables on fire performance is finally evaluated and discussed in a parametric study. This analysis yields valuable insights crucial for an effective design of the planned fire tests on CFDST columns using high-strength steel, as detailed in the next section.

3 FORESEEN EXPERIMENTAL TEST IN FIRE

3.1 General

To assess the actual load-bearing resistance of CFDST columns using high-strength steels in fire conditions, an experimental test is planned, and the respective setup and procedure is described below. The exact geometry of the two foreseen test specimens is currently being evaluated and the current contribution may provide valuable results to ease the decision process.

3.2 Setup and testing procedure

The test setup of the planned fire test is schematically illustrated in Fig. 2(a). The furnace thermally isolated by means of refractory bricks and ceramic fibre blankets while the vertical loading is applied onto the specimen via a 1MN hydraulic jack. This is fixed on the upper side of the testing rig at an eccentricity $e=H/500$ about the weak axis of the specimen in accordance with EN 1365-4 [13], see Fig. 2(b), where H indicates the total height of the column.

Fig. 2: (a) Setup of the fire test and (b) cross-sectional view including the location of the load

Further details on the instrumentation will be provided in a future publication whereas the current contribution focuses on the preliminary design of the specimen through a finite element (FE) model described below.

4 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

4.1 General

The numerical simulations were conducted using Abaqus software to study the nonlinear mechanical and thermal behaviour of the columns. The model was created assembling three independent parts, as shown in Fig. 3a: the outer tube in red, the concrete in green, and the inner tube in grey.

The mesh definition (Fig. 3b) was performed independently for each component. The outer tube was divided into 3 tangential elements (1), the inner tube, being thicker, was divided into 4 tangential elements (3), while the concrete ring presents a much finer mesh composed of 15 tangential elements (2), since the thermal gradient in this element is very high. Radially, the section was divided into 18 segments (4), each with an amplitude of 20° . Based on preliminary analysis and available numerical studies on steel columns, a mesh edge size of 20 mm was chosen along the longitudinal direction. The simulations were conducted using 3D solid elements for each of the three parts of the column. For mechanical simulations, an 8-node linear brick with reduced integration (C3D8R) was used, instead for thermal analysis, an 8-node linear heat transfer brick (DC3D8) was employed.

Fig. 3: (a) 3D view of the FE model of CDFST columns and (b) cross-sectional view of the mesh

4.2 Thermal properties

The thermal properties required for conducting thermal analysis of materials include thermal conductivity, density, and specific heat. These parameters are temperature-dependent and are defined for both steel and concrete in EN 1994-1-2 [14].

The specific heat of concrete is defined through a simple linear relationship in Eurocode 4, which predicts a peak around 100°C due to the evaporation of free water present in the cementitious matrix. However, it is important to note that the graph of heat capacity as a function of temperature predicts a second peak around 700°C. This peak is caused by an endothermic reaction resulting from the decomposition of dolomite, which absorbs a large amount of energy.

The fire protection American Standards' appendix [15] proposes a more accurate formulation of specific heat as a function of temperature, which takes into consideration both of the previously mentioned peaks. Therefore, it is preferred in this study to the one proposed by the Eurocode.

4.3 Temperature-dependent mechanical properties

In Abaqus, materials are defined by specifying their elastic and inelastic mechanical properties. When analysing fire situations, it is important to consider the temperature-dependent mechanical properties of materials, as recommended in EN 1994-1-2 [14].

The stress-strain relationship for the steel was modelled in accordance with Eurocode 3 guidelines. Engineering stress-strain values were initially derived, followed by true stress-strain values. The elastic modulus values used refer to the initial secant elastic modulus. To account for the variability of the mechanical properties of steel in the absence of material-specific mechanical tests, the yield strength, ultimate strength, and elastic modulus values were adjusted according to the guidance in Table E.1 prEN 1993-1-1 [16]. The model used in Abaqus for steel modelling follows the von Mises failure criterion and the associated plastic flow rule [17].

The Concrete Damaged Plasticity (CDP) model, present in Abaqus, defines the constitutive relationship of concrete. To model the plastic properties of concrete through the CDP, three sets of numerical data related to concrete properties must be defined. The first and second sets concern the compressive and tensile behaviour of concrete, which in this case were modelled according to EN 1992-1-1 [18]. The third set defines the failure surface of concrete elements using five plasticity parameters: the dilation angle (ψ), the biaxial-to-uniaxial compressive strength ratio (f_{b0}/f_{co}), eccentricity of the potential surface (ε), shape factor of the yield function (K) and the viscosity parameter (μ) [19]. Standard values of plasticity parameters for concrete are considered in this study as defined in [20] whereas damage modelling was neglected.

Table 1. Plasticity parameters for CDP model

Dilation angle ψ	f_{b0}/f_{co}	Eccentricity ε	Shape factor K	Viscosity parameter μ
31	1.16	0.1	0.67	0.001

4.4 Thermal conditions

The thermal analysis carried out on CFDSCs is of the transient heat transfer type. Heat is transferred from the surface of the outer tube to that of the inner tube. Heat transfer from the fire to the column is by convection and radiation, following a heating curve according to the Standards ISO 834-1 [21]. For standard fire conditions, EN 1994-1-2 [14] recommend to use a convection coefficient of $h_v = 25 \text{ W/m}^2\text{K}$ and an emissivity $\varepsilon_m = 0.7$ for both steel and concrete elements. Finally, full heat transfer among different materials at the contact interfaces was enabled by the feature *TIE.

4.5 Boundary conditions and contact properties

In order to correctly apply the mechanical boundary conditions at the ends of the column, i.e. to ensure a realistic application of the load, the end cross-sections were kinematically coupled with the corresponding reference points. The following boundary conditions were applied:

- At the top, the transversal deformations were restrained in both directions (U1 and U2) as well as the torsional rotation (UR3). The axial displacement (U3) and the bending rotations (UR1, UR2) were kept free;
- At the bottom, all the translations (U1, U2, U3) and rotations around the longitudinal axis (UR3) were restrained. Depending on the test setup, the rotations about both bending axes (UR1, UR2) may be released.

The vertical load was applied concentrically on the top reference point, so that the vertical force is distributed over the whole upper surface of the column. In addition, a geometrical imperfection of the column was implemented in the FE model based on the first buckling mode using an amplitude of $L/1000$, as recommended in prEN1993-1-14 [22] for geometrically and materially non-linear analyses (GMNIA), where L indicates the length of the member.

Finally, the three main instances of the FE model shown in Fig. 3 were assembled to form the CFDST column. To ensure the transfer of the forces arising at the interfaces between the materials, a simplified tie constraint was established. This enforces the rigid connection of the two bonded surfaces without allowing any, albeit realistic, relative slip displacement. The suitability of the proposed approach is verified in the following section with the support of past experimental tests.

4.6 Validation (Transient thermomechanical analysis)

To ensure an appropriate modelling of the thermal and mechanical properties and the contact conditions, transient thermomechanical analysis was carried out to predict the structural response of the member exposed to time-dependent temperature increase. The procedure is illustrated in the flow-chart of Fig. 4.

Fig. 4: Transient analysis workflow

First, a bifurcation analysis (LBA) is performed to determine the critical buckling mode and the respective geometrical imperfections. In parallel, a heat transfer analysis (HTA) is conducted to extrapolate the temperature distribution in the members over time. Both output data are finally combined in a static analysis subjected to the time-dependent temperature field of the respective HTA. In this case, the vertical load remains constant while the temperature field varies over time. This approach allows to extract the fire resistance period, i.e. the duration for which the column can withstand the given load. The numerically-obtained results were compared with the reference test “H2” of the experimental campaign on CFDST columns documented by Wan et al. in [10]. The geometry and the main material properties are indicated below in *Table 2*. Both inner and outer tube

were first welded to two square steel end plate after concrete casting to ensure the concentric introduction of the vertical load onto the specimen.

Table 2. Data of the experimental test considered for the validation

Outer tube			Concrete	Inner tube		
Dimensions [mm]	Length [m]	Yield strength [MPa]	Compressive strength [MPa]	Dimensions [mm]	Yield strength [MPa]	
325x6.0	3.8	275	46.8	159x6.0	260	

The upper limits of the axial displacement u_{max} and the displacement rate given in EN 1363-1 in fire conditions are considered to define the failure conditions and they are as follows:

$$u_{max} = \frac{H}{100} \quad (1)$$

$$\left| \frac{du}{dt} \right|_{max} = \frac{3H}{100} \left[\frac{mm}{min} \right] \quad (2)$$

Where u is the vertical displacement in mm and H is the total column height in mm.

The results of the thermal and the transient thermomechanical simulation are summarized in terms of temperature θ and vertical displacement u in Fig. 5(a) and Fig. 5(b), respectively, together with the corresponding experimental measurements. As can be seen, a good agreement between measured and numerical values of the temperature can be found with a deviation not exceeding 50 °C. The time-dependent temperature field of the whole composite column was subsequently extracted and implemented in the mechanical model (i.e. transient thermomechanical simulation) together with a predefined bow imperfection with a given amplitude of L/1000.

Fig. 5: Results of the thermal and thermomechanical validation of the column test H1 [10]

From the vertical displacement-time graph in Fig. 5(b), it can be concluded that the fire resistance period, i.e. the time at which the deformation exceeds the allowable value u_{max} , is perfectly captured by the numerical model and it is approximately 69 minutes. However, the discrepancy between the experimental and numerical curve is attributed to the neglect of the thermal expansion in the FE model. Owing to convergence issues, the thermal expansion has not been successfully implemented in this model. Notably, this aspect does not affect the steady-state thermomechanical analyses presented in the next section.

Based on the accuracy of the FE model in predicting the actual fire resistance period of the tested CFDST column, the presented model is finally used to perform a parametric study aiming to support the design and optimization of the specimen shortly described in Section 2.

4.7 Parametric study (Steady-state thermomechanical analysis)

Unlike transient analysis, an alternative “steady-state” numerical procedure is presented in this section and it enables the direct computation of the maximum load at given fire resistance period. As the name “Steady-state” suggests, this analysis evaluates the thermal equilibrium of a system where a given system property, i.e. temperature field, remains constant over time. Specifically, the approach consists in a static GMNIA analysis using a predefined temperature field extracted at a given time (e.g. 30, 60 or 90 minutes) from the companion heat transfer analysis (HTA). Fig. 6 illustrates the schematically the main steps taken to conduct this analysis. Once the requested “target” fire resistance time is defined, the corresponding temperature field is extrapolated and implemented in the static analysis. Finally, the load is gradually increased up to failure.

Fig. 6: Steady-state analysis workflow

Compared to the transient analysis, this procedure is more efficient and faster to deliver a reliable estimate the maximum load at a given fire resistance rating. This represents a valuable tool to optimize the geometry and the material choice of the CFDST column for the foreseen fire test described in Section 3. Therefore, the respective setup in Fig. 2 was considered in this preliminary study. Owing to the geometrical limitations of the furnace, the length of the column was kept equal to 3.3 m and the column foot was considered fixed in all cases. Additionally, expected values of the mechanical properties, i.e. mean values of strength and stiffness, were adopted in the FE model.

As confirmed by the previous transient analysis, the outer tube of CFDST columns underwent earlier deterioration of its mechanical properties compared to the inner elements as a result of its direct exposure to fire. Although its bending stiffness remains a fundamental parameter to prevent early flexural buckling, it becomes evident that the load is mainly transferred through the inner steel tube shielded by the sandwiched layer. Based on these considerations, different steel grades of inner tube and the following interlayer materials were investigated: conventional concrete, low-weight concrete and a cement-free mixture patented under the name “Cleancrete[®]” [23], whose thermal properties were reported in [24]. Additionally, two different outer tube geometries were considered. The list of the parameters investigated is summarized in Table 3 leading to a total of 24 different configurations.

Table 3. Parameters of the numerical study

Outer tube		Interlayer material	Inner tube	
Dimensions [mm]	Grade		Dimensions [mm]	Grade
152.4x5	S355	Concrete C30/37	88.9x11	S235, S460, S690, S890
159x4		Lightweight concrete LC/16		
		Cleancrete [®]		

4.8 Results and discussion

Based on the steady-state thermomechanical simulations of the 24 configurations listed in Table 3, the expected resistance was investigated after 30-, 60- and 90-minute fire exposure. To visualize the impact of the three main parameters, i.e. inner tube yield strength, sandwiched material and outer tube diameter, three respective plots are given in Fig. 7. All plots refer to the base configuration “152.4x5-S355-Concrete C30/37-88.9x11-S235” where only one of the parameters were varied.

Fig. 7: Influence of (a) inner tube yield strength and (b) interlayer material after 30, 60 and 90 minutes of fire exposure

As shown in Fig. 7(a), the use of high-strength steels in the inner tube of CFDST columns enhances significantly the fire resistance. However, this increase becomes less important beyond S690 grades. The sandwiched layer protecting the inner tube represents another key factor affecting the performance of the column in fire conditions, as can be seen in Fig. 7(b). However, the application of lightweight concrete LC16/18 results in comparable resistance values regardless of the fire rating. A smaller resistance is achieved when using cement-free concrete due to its low mechanical strength and stiffness. It becomes evident that a careful use of high-strength steels may compensate for the resistance loss caused by the adoption of innovative cement-free mixtures as sandwiched layer. To quantify the effect of these two parameters on the fire resistance, the relative increase in percentage is given in Table 4, including the results at ambient temperature. S690 steel grade represents an optimal solution with a relative increase of the fire resistance up to +43.2% after 60 minutes exposure. Notably, the enhancement is more pronounced at elevated temperature (+30÷43%) compared to ambient temperature (ca. +28%) which is in line with the considerations in Section 2. Finally, a marginal increase in strength was observed by changing the outer tube dimensions from 152.4x5 mm to 159.0x4 mm. Based on the outcomes of this numerical study, a S690 steel tube will be employed as inner tube in the foreseen experimental fire test while the use of an alternative interlayer material is still under consideration.

Table 4. Fire resistance increase in percentage for different inner tube steel grade and interlayer materials

Fire-rating	Inner tube steel grade				Interlayer material		
	S235	S460	S690	S890	C30/37	LC16/18	Cleancrete
R0 (Ambient)	-	+18.4%	+28.0%	+30.8%	-	-5.2%	-18.7%
R30	-	+29.3%	+42.4%	+47.8%	-	-5.2%	-18.7%
R60	-	+26.3%	+43.2%	+51.4%	-	+5.0%	-24.4%
R90	-	+18.9%	+32.9%	+40.1%	-	-6.8%	-38.4%

5 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The current contribution presents and assess numerically the potential of employing high-strength steels in CDFST columns at elevated temperature in order to optimize the geometry and material choice of a full-scale specimen to be tested in fire. First, a finite element (FE) model is presented and thoroughly described for predicting the thermal and thermomechanical response of CDFST columns. The suitability of the FE model is also validated against an experimental test of a concentrically-loaded CDFST columns subjected to fire via a transient thermomechanical analysis.

The geometry was adapted to the dimensions of interest of the specimen while the influence of several interlayer materials and high-strength steel on the expected peak load was evaluated by performing several steady-state analyses at predefined time step (e.g. at 30, 60 or 90 minutes of fire exposure).

This study shows that the adoption of high-strength steel for the inner tube results in a substantial enhancement of the load-bearing resistance of the CDFST column in fire, with S690 steel being a promising option reaching an increase of ca. 42% and 43%, after 60 and 90 minutes, respectively. Furthermore, the use of light-weight concrete delivers similar results whereas the adoption of cement-free concrete could reduce the fire resistance by ca. 25% compared to conventional concrete.

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